

STUDIES IN LONG-CHAIN ACIDS. PART I. AN EXTENSION OF THE ISOPRENE RULE.

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The isoprene rule has been extended so as to explain the formation of some 12- and 16-carbon acids occurring in nature.

Isoprene has been long recognised as one of the chief building units utilised by nature in the synthesis of plant products and also to a lesser extent in the synthesis of animal products.

The formation of larger molecules from isoprene is assumed to occur in one of the three following ways :—

(1) By direct linear head to tail union, a polymerisation which may result in either acyclic or cyclic hydrocarbons and which is generally recognised as the origin of the terpenes $(C_5H_8)_n$.

(2) By a similar type of polymerisation with concurrent hydrogenation which would explain the formation of such hydrocarbons as that from which the alcohol, phytol $(C_{20}H_{40}O)$ is derived.

(3) By addition with accompanying dehydrogenation in 1:4 position,

These C_5H_8 units then combine to longer chains as in the carotenoids. (Kuhn and Winterstein, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1928, **11**, 430).

The formation of a large number of long-chain aliphatic acids, both mono- and dibasic can be explained if to the above three we add a fourth category namely :—

(4) Head to tail union of isoprene units ; addition of H_2O at a conjugated double bond at one end of the chain ; partial or complete hydrogenation and removal of side-chain methyl groups by oxidation and oxidation, complete or partial, of the terminal groups.

The facts which led to this hypothesis are briefly these: Kerschbaum (*Ber.*, 1927, **60**, 902), had detected the presence of farnesol along with ambrettolid in musk kernel oil and in connection with our work on aleuritic and ambrettolic acids (to be published later) we were anxious to connect the presence of farnesol with that of the lactone ambrettolid. Now, the constitution of ambrettolic acid (*loc. cit.*) has been found to be

